

**Leveraging distributed systems to foster research initiatives in educational institutions and small
businesses**

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Abstract

The advent of big data and the increasing demand for data-driven insights have propelled the field of data science to the forefront of modern research and innovation. To keep pace with the rapidly evolving data landscape, the establishment of research hubs within educational institutions and small enterprises has emerged as a strategic approach to harness the full potential of data science.

This paper emphasizes the importance of research hubs in driving data science advancements within schools, universities and small businesses. By establishing such hubs, institutions and enterprises can facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, enabling experts from diverse fields to collectively tackle complex problems and leverage their combined expertise to deliver robust and impactful solutions.

Moreover, incorporating distributed systems within these hubs proves instrumental in overcoming the challenges posed by the sheer volume and complexity of data. Distributed systems enable the seamless integration of data from various sources and provide efficient processing capabilities to manage, analyze and interpret large-scale datasets. As a result, researchers and data scientists can expedite their workflows, minimize processing bottlenecks and gain valuable insights more effectively.

Furthermore, the utilization of distributed systems fosters a culture of continuous learning and growth. By providing access to shared resources and tools, research hubs can empower students, researchers and employees to enhance their data science skills, thus nurturing a new generation of data-driven professionals.

Keywords: Clustering, Data Science, Machine Learning, Education

Introduction

Technological development throughout the world is advancing at an increasingly rapid pace, which compels educational institutions and businesses to adapt their training and projects to the demanding pace of the labor market.

While computer science is already taught from an early age, school curriculums often focus on using office applications, some basic concepts about systems and introductions to programming.

The ever-changing world of technology even poses challenges for universities to present an updated educational path where subjects are interconnected, rather than isolated blocks of knowledge that never seem to fit into a larger-scale project.

To address this issue, many institutions adopt an educational system based on projects throughout the academic year. Students begin with a few solid foundations and gradually add layers of complexity to the original idea as the year progresses.

However, this still leaves a significant gap between the world of education and the professional world since even the most elaborate projects during the student's educational journey are far from what they will face in their daily work life.

This situation becomes even more problematic when it comes to teaching newer branches of science and technology. For instance, we can observe how data science, machine learning and artificial

intelligence are increasingly present in everyday life, but there are hardly enough trained professionals to develop such projects.

Part of this issue arises from the fact that there are few educators with a solid background in these fields due to their recent high demand in the market. Additionally, many educational centers lack the capabilities to develop more than small experiments due to the significant hardware and time requirements involved in executing algorithms with medium-sized data volumes.

The business world faces similar challenges because while companies with large budgets can afford to have professionals and teams in the aforementioned areas, many small or medium-sized enterprises cannot bear the costs of running these processes in the cloud or having their hardware, which limits their innovative and competitive capabilities.

This is where the role of the distributed systems hub becomes crucial. It is an attempt to offer educational centers and budget-limited businesses an option to reuse the equipment they already have as clusters for executing complex algorithms.

By doing so, the aim is to enhance the accessibility of these groups to higher-level hardware that is easy to scale and flexible, without being tied to a cloud provider and its service costs. Owning their own research cluster will also enable them to acquire better technical skills that can be transferred to larger projects later on.

What is a cluster?

A "cluster" is a term used in the field of computing and technology to refer to a set of interconnected computers or servers that work together as if they were a single processing unit. These machines, called nodes, collaborate to perform tasks and solve problems more efficiently and with greater processing capacity than if they worked individually.

Clusters are widely used in various fields for different purposes, such as processing massive amounts of data, running high-demand computational applications, hosting high-traffic websites, scientific simulation, artificial intelligence, machine learning and other applications that require significant processing power.

The key features of a cluster are:

- **Interconnection:** The nodes in the cluster are connected to each other through high-speed networks, enabling fast and efficient communication between them.
- **High availability:** Clusters are designed to be highly redundant, meaning that if one or more nodes fail, others can take on their workload to maintain service continuity.
- **Scalability:** Clusters are generally scalable, allowing for the addition of more nodes to increase their processing capacity and performance.

- **Parallelism:** Clusters often work in parallel, dividing complex tasks into smaller subtasks that can be executed simultaneously on multiple nodes, thereby accelerating processing time.
- **Centralized management:** Clusters are usually centrally managed and controlled to facilitate configuration, monitoring and resource administration.

In summary, a cluster is a grouping of computers that work together to solve high-complexity computational tasks, providing greater efficiency and performance than if they were used individually.

Hardware requirements for each field

The types of problems in data science, machine learning and artificial intelligence that can be addressed depend on the hardware's computational power, specifically the number of cores and RAM available. Here are some examples based on the hardware specifications:

1. **Small-scale Data Analysis:** With a dual-core or quad-core processor and around 4GB to 8GB of RAM, small-scale data analysis tasks, such as basic data cleaning, exploratory data analysis and simple statistical modeling, can be efficiently handled.
2. **Simple Machine Learning Models:** For basic machine learning tasks like linear regression, decision trees and k-nearest neighbors, a quad-core processor with 8GB to 16GB of RAM is usually sufficient.

Use cases:

- **Predictive Analytics:** Data science and machine learning can be used to build predictive models that forecast future trends and outcomes. This is used in areas such as sales forecasting and demand prediction.
 - **Customer Churn Prediction:** Data science and machine learning can help businesses predict and prevent customer churn by identifying at-risk customers.
3. **Medium-scale Data Processing:** To work with medium-sized datasets and more sophisticated algorithms like clustering, classification and regression, a quad-core to octa-core processor with 16GB to 32GB of RAM is recommended.

Use cases:

- Recommendation Systems: These technologies are commonly employed in recommendation engines for personalized content and product recommendations, as seen on platforms like Netflix, Amazon and Spotify.
- Anomaly Detection: Data science and machine learning can detect unusual patterns or outliers in data, which is useful in fraud detection, fault detection in industrial processes and network intrusion detection.
- Social Media Analysis: AI and data science are used to analyze social media data for sentiment analysis, trend prediction and understanding customer preferences.
- Financial Analysis: Data science and machine learning are used in credit risk assessment, fraud detection, algorithmic trading and financial market analysis.

4. Deep Learning with GPUs: Deep learning tasks, especially neural networks, benefit significantly from GPUs. For training complex models on larger datasets, a system equipped with a powerful GPU (e.g., NVIDIA GTX/RTX series or NVIDIA A100) and 32GB to 64GB of RAM is preferable.

Use cases:

- Image and Video Analysis: Machine learning and AI can be applied to analyze and interpret images and videos, enabling tasks like object recognition, facial recognition and content tagging.

- Natural Language Processing (NLP): NLP allows computers to understand and interpret human language. It is used in chatbots, sentiment analysis, language translation and text summarization.
 - Speech Recognition: AI-based speech recognition systems are used in virtual assistants, voice-activated devices and transcription services.
5. Large-scale Data Analytics: The hardware may include multiple nodes, each with octa-core processors and 64GB to 128GB of RAM or more.
- Uses cases:
- Resource Optimization: Machine learning can optimize resource allocation and utilization in areas like supply chain management, energy consumption and transportation logistics.
6. High-performance Computing (HPC): For demanding AI tasks like complex simulations or scientific research, HPC clusters with multiple processors (e.g., multi-core CPUs or GPUs) and large memory capacities (e.g., hundreds of gigabytes or terabytes) are necessary.
- Use cases:
- Healthcare: These technologies are applied in medical image analysis, disease prediction, drug discovery and personalized medicine.

Hardware specifications mentioned above are general guidelines and can vary depending on the specific algorithms, dataset sizes and the complexity of the tasks. As technology evolves, hardware capabilities are continually improving, allowing for more significant and complex data science, machine learning and AI applications. Even with that, we can observe how, by using a local cluster, we can go from being able to work between level 1 (Small-scale Data Analysis) and level 2 (Simple Machine Learning Models) to a level 4 (Deep Learning with GPUs) or even 5 (Large-scale Data Analytics), depending on the hardware of the nodes. This is a great advantage for small research teams, educational centers, or companies that can allocate a few machines to create this infrastructure.

Considering machines with 4 cores, 8 GB of RAM and a GPU, it would only be necessary to interconnect 4, plus an extra one to act as a scheduler and we would be able to work at level 4 for cases where the problem can be distributed.

Furthermore, since these machines, when not running the algorithms, can be used for any other function (office work, web browsing, etc.), they are not computers that remain dedicated solely to this specific purpose.

Utilization of existing systems

While the initial drawback of creating a cluster is the upfront investment in hardware (servers, switches, network cables, etc.), this equipment is already accessible in most educational institutions and small businesses.

To present a straightforward scenario, let's consider examples where a computer lab or office has computers with 4 cores and 8GB of RAM each. Although a computer with these specifications may not be capable of handling data science, machine learning or artificial intelligence problems on its own due to the intensive resource requirements of these disciplines, they can be useful when working together.

To achieve this, we will use a setup that includes a scheduler (project manager) and several workers (computers that will attempt to solve different parts of the problem). The role of the scheduler is to divide the problem into smaller blocks and distribute them among the workers. It also monitors the health status of the computers during execution to assign them new tasks as they complete their current assignments. Once the work packages are finished, the scheduler will gather the solutions and reunify them.

[Scheduler/Worker Setup]

Through this approach, a group of low-power computers can tackle problems that would be unattainable for each individual machine due to their hardware limitations.

In this way, a computer lab in a school can provide basic training to its students on data science and then carry out practical projects on the cluster, allowing them to work on projects that would otherwise be unthinkable without a significant financial investment. Taking this idea further, a series of public or private institutions can donate their outdated equipment to create a hub that they will subsequently use together. This is a way to emulate, on a smaller scale, the functioning of research centers where powerful machines can be reserved by researchers to conduct experiments that would simply be unfeasible with their day-to-day equipment.

Moreover, institutions such as technical training centers or universities can also repurpose available equipment to provide their students with experiences closer to the work environment or to grant their researchers access to more powerful hardware within the university's resources, without having to queue for access to supercomputers whose resources they might not fully utilize.

Thus, an internal research cluster offers access to resources several times greater than what a student or researcher's personal computer can provide, but it does not replace the need for access to supercomputing hardware for tackling the most complex problems. Fortunately, a significant portion of research problems can be handled using this intermediate approach.

This approach is also suitable for companies that want to have some independence in the use of intensive hardware. The analysis of each case depends on its specific circumstances, but certain points must be considered:

- Having such a system reduces processing times, leading to more tests, shorter waiting times, or reduced costs from errors. The earlier a poorly designed algorithm is discovered, the more time the company has to correct it before final delivery.
- Implementing a cluster incurs costs related to the implementation time, electricity and necessary hardware. If the hardware is already available, the other two costs can be quite minimal. There are free libraries available in various programming languages that allow the deployment and configuration of this infrastructure within hours. Regarding electricity costs, the

power consumption of the equipment remains the same whether they are used separately or together.

- Having a cluster enables working with larger datasets, reinforcing the results obtained by studying a larger universe of data.
- Skills in distributed processing, machine interconnection and monitoring are highly sought-after in an increasingly digitalized world.
- The computers designated for the cluster can be added or removed for other uses as needed.

For example, computers in a classroom can function as a cluster when required, but minutes later, they can be used as independent machines for other tasks since their physical separation is always maintained.

Conclusion

The creation of research hubs within educational institutions and small businesses represents a vital step toward maximizing the potential of data science. By leveraging distributed systems, these hubs can harness the collective intelligence of interdisciplinary teams, efficiently handle vast amounts of data and foster a culture of collaboration and innovation. Ultimately, the synergy between research hubs and distributed systems is pivotal in advancing data science and driving transformative societal impact across diverse domains.

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